

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Zirconium(IV) with n-Capric Acid

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A selective method has been developed for reversed phase extraction chromatographic studies of zirconium(IV) with high molecular weight carboxylic acid, n-capric acid as a stationary phase on a column of silica gel. Quantitative extraction of zirconium(IV) has been achieved from 0.01 M acetic acid solution in the pH range 2.5–5.0. The extracted zirconium(IV) has been stripped with nitric acid (4 M) and estimated spectrophotometrically. The effect of variables as pH, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. Exchange capacity of the exchanger and breakthrough capacity have been determined. Zirconium(IV) has been separated from various elements. Zirconium(IV) has also been separated from several synthetic multicomponent mixtures.

A large number of papers have been published on the extraction of metals with high molecular weight carboxylic acids^{1,2}. n-Capric acid, a C₁₀ monocarboxylic acid in benzene, has been used for solvent extraction of zinc and cadmium from aqueous solutions³. The extraction of zirconium(IV) with Amberlite LA-1⁴ and laurohydroxamic acid⁵ has been reported. The extraction chromatographic behaviour of zirconium(IV) on a silica gel column impregnated with carboxylic acid (versatic 10) has also been reported⁶ but the extraction chromatographic studies of zirconium(IV) with n-capric acid has not yet been reported. Therefore, this communication presents the systematic studies on the extraction chromatographic behaviour of zirconium(IV) on silica gel column coated with n-capric acid.

Results and Discussion

The systematic studies on extraction chromatographic behaviour of zirconium(IV) with capric acid at pH 0.5–5.0 from acetate buffer showed that Zr^{IV} was quantitatively extracted at pH 2.5–5.0. Flow rates up to 2.5 ml min⁻¹ during extraction showed the complete retention of Zr^{IV} in the column.

After extraction, Zr^{IV} was stripped with various mineral acids. The results are given in Table 1. Complete stripping of Zr^{IV} was achieved with 5.5

M HCl and 4 M HNO₃. H₂SO₄ was not used for stripping as it interferes. HCl (5.5 M) can not be used repeatedly for stripping as it changes the exchange behaviour of the exchanger. It was found that nitric acid (4 M) gave the best stripping, hence it was used as eluent in all the experiments.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF STRIPPING AGENTS FOR REMOVAL Zr^{IV}
Zr^{IV} taken = 80.4 µg, Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 2.5

Eluent	Concn M	Peak elution vol (V _{max}) ml	Total vol of eluent (V _t) ml	Recovery %
HCl	0.5	35	55	12
	1.0	30	50	25
	2.0	25	40	32
	3.0	25	35	45
	4.0	20	30	65
	4.5	15	25	85
	5.5	10	20	100
HNO ₃	0.1	30	50	0.10
	0.2	25	45	0.25
	1.0	20	40	55
	2.5	15	30	80
	3.5	12.5	20	95
	4.0	10	20	100

Breakthrough capacity, i.e. the number of milliequivalent of ions which can be retained without any leakage being observed with respect to Zr^{IV} in capric acid coated on silica gel, was determined

at pH 2.5 and 5.0. An exchanger bed was prepared from 1.0 g of the prepared exchanger. The pH of the exchanger bed and zirconium solution (2.5 mg ml⁻¹) was adjusted to the desired value with the acetate buffer and then the solution was passed through the column. It was found that the leakage of Zr^{IV} started at pH 2.5 and 5.0 after passing 16 ml and 24 ml of the effluent respectively. Hence the uptake of Zr^{IV} increases with increase in pH. The maximum amount of Zr^{IV} loaded quantitatively by capric acid impregnated on silica gel at pH 2.5 and 5.0 are 40 and 60 mg respectively. A plot of C/C₀ (where C₀ and C are the concentrations of Zr^{IV} in influent and effluent respectively) against volume of effluent is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Breakthrough curves of Zr^{IV} on silica gel coated with capric acid.

Separation of Zr^{IV} from binary mixtures : It was possible to separate Zr^{IV} from elements in binary mixture by exploiting the differences in pH for extraction and also by the differences in stripping characteristics. At pH 2.5 elements like Mg^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ce^{IV}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV} could not form acetate complex, they passed through the column but Zr^{IV} was extracted. After extraction, Zr^{IV} was eluted with 4 M HNO₃. The separation of Zr^{IV} from binary mixtures containing Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Al^{III} or Pd^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture

at pH 5.0 when each of the foreign ions along with Zr^{IV} were extracted. In all cases the other was eluted first with specific eluents, like Cu^{II} was stripped with 0.01 M HNO₃, Hg^{II} with 0.2 M HNO₃, Pb^{II} with 0.01 M HNO₃, Al^{III} with 0.1 M HNO₃ and Pd^{II} with 0.25 M HCl, later Zr^{IV} was stripped with 4 M HNO₃. Zr^{IV} was separated from Fe^{III} by passing the mixture at pH 2.5 while both the elements were selectively extracted. After extraction Fe^{III} was stripped first with 0.1 M HCl and then Zr^{IV} with 4 M HNO₃. After separation, Zr^{IV} was determined spectrophotometrically while the foreign ions were estimated complexometrically⁷. The results of binary separation are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Zr^{IV} FROM BINARY MIXTURES

Zr^{IV} = 80.4 µg, Column = 0.8 × 8 cm, Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 2.5

Metal	Metal added mg	Metal recovered mg	Recovery of Zr ^{IV} µg
Mg ^{II}	2.14	2.12	80.8
Cr ^{III}	2.0	1.98	80.6
Mn ^{II}	2.36	2.35	80.6
Co ^{II}	4.18	4.22	80.0
Ni ^{II}	2.06	2.08	80.0
Zn ^{II}	2.45	2.41	80.8
Cd ^{II}	2.30	2.28	80.6
Ce ^{IV}	2.50	2.52	80.2
La ^{III}	2.64	2.60	80.8
Pr ^{III}	2.10	2.08	80.6
Nd ^{III}	2.20	2.22	80.0
Gd ^{III}	2.58	2.6	80.2
Sm ^{III}	2.10	2.12	80.0
Dy ^{III}	3.6	3.62	80.2
U ^{VI}	3.5	3.48	80.6
Th ^{IV}	2.62	2.60	80.8
Fe ^{III}	4.53	4.50	80.6
Cu ^{IIa}	1.5	1.48	80.6
Hg ^{IIa}	2.7	2.72	80.2
Pb ^{IIa}	3.0	2.96	80.6
Al ^{IIIa}	3.5	3.48	80.6
Pd ^{IIa}	3.04	3.06	80.0

^apH = 5.0

Separation of Zr^{IV} from synthetic mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical applications, the proposed method has been applied to separate Zr^{IV} from several synthetic mixtures containing Fe^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Pb^{II} etc. In almost all the cases,

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF Zr^{IV} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURESZr^{IV} taken = 80.4 µg, Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 5.0

Sl no	Cation	Weight added (recovered)	Relative error %	Eluent used	Eluent volume ml
1 ^a	Co ^{II}	2060 (2070)	+0.49	—	—
	Fe ^{III}	4530 (4520)	-0.22	0.1 M HCl	25
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (80.6)	+0.25	4 M HNO ₃	20
2 ^a	U ^{VI}	3500 (3520)	+0.57	—	—
	Fe ^{III}	4530 (4510)	-0.44	0.1 M HCl	25
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (80.2)	-0.25	4 M HNO ₃	20
3 ^a	Ce ^{IV}	2500 (2520)	+0.80	—	—
	Fe ^{III}	4530 (4500)	-0.66	0.1 M HCl	25
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (80.8)	+0.50	4 M HNO ₃	20
4	U ^{VI}	3500 (3530)	+0.86	0.001 M HNO ₃	20
	Th ^{IV}	2620 (2590)	-1.15	0.25 M HNO ₃	45
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (80.6)	+0.25	4 M HNO ₃	20
5	U ^{VI}	3500 (3530)	+0.86	0.001 M HNO ₃	20
	Th ^{IV}	2620 (2580)	-1.53	0.25 M HNO ₃	45
	Ce ^{IV}	2500 (2510)	+0.40	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	25
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (80.0)	-0.50	4 M HNO ₃	20
6	Zn ^{II}	2450 (2460)	+0.41	—	—
	Pb ^{II}	3000 (2980)	-0.67	0.002 M HNO ₃	25
	Hg ^{II}	2720 (2730)	+0.37	0.2 M HNO ₃	25
	Zr ^{IV}	80.4 (79.0)	-1.74	4 M HNO ₃	20

^apH = 2.5

quantitative extractions and separations were achieved.

The results of separation of zirconium(IV) from synthetic mixtures are given in Table 3.

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and permits separation of Zr^{IV} from Pb^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} which is very important as these elements are associated in various minerals, ores and fission products. The overall time required for extraction and separation does not exceed 2.5 h.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter provided with glass and saturated calomel electrodes, Beckman DU-6 and ECIL GS 5700A spectrophotometers, a hot-cum-cold bath (Dimmerstat 7D-IF) and chromatographic column (i.d. 0.8 cm) of borosil glass with glass wool plug at the bottom were used.

Capric acid (C.R., Wako Chemical Industries,

Japan), a C₁₀ monocarboxylic acid was used as the liquid cation exchanger.

A stock solution of Zr^{IV} (2.5 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving ZrO(NO₃)₂ (AnalaR) in HNO₃ and diluted it to 100 ml with deionised water and standardised complexometrically⁸. A solution containing 80.4 µg ml⁻¹ of Zr^{IV} was prepared through appropriate dilution. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from acetic acid (0.01 M) and ammonium acetate (0.01 M).

Preparation of ion-exchange material : Silica gel (60–120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapour of dimethyldichlorosilane in an atmosphere of nitrogen for about 3 h, then washed with anhydrous methanol and dried at 100⁰⁹. 1 ml of dimethyldichlorosilane was found to be adequate for 10 g of silica gel. 1 g gel could take up about 0.9 ml of n-capric acid. The silica gel was coated by treatment with a benzene solution of capric acid and the excess solvent was

TABLE 4—EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF CAPRIC ACID COATED ON SILICA GEL

Shaking time = 10 h.

Temp. °C	Amount of exchanger g	Volume of 2.5 N NaCl ml	Volume of 0.2 N NaOH ml	Volume of deionised ml	Exchange capa- city meq. of H ⁺ /g
25	1.002	20	15	15	2.04
35	1.003	20	15	15	2.05
40	1.002	20	15	15	2.06
50	1.001	20	15	15	2.10
60	0.992	20	15	15	2.12

evaporated on rotary vacuum evaporator. A slurry of the coated silica gel in distilled water was prepared by centrifugation at 1500 rpm and then poured into a chromatographic column (i.d. = 0.8 cm) to give a bed-height of 8 cm. The bed was washed with 1 M HCl to remove excess of organic solvent. Silica gel was found suitable for the support as it was porous and able to retain a considerable amount of the exchanger. Each column was suitable for at least 25 cycles without any loss of exchange capacity.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of milligram equivalents of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in the hydrogen -form. The dry exchanger (1 g) was mixed with a solution (50 ml) containing 2.5 N NaCl (20 ml), 0.2 N NaOH (15 ml) and deionised water (15 ml) and then shaken for 10 h in a hot-cum-cold bath. The liberated hydrogen ion reacted with NaOH and excess NaOH was determined titrimetrically with 0.2 N HCl. The results are given in Table 4.

General extraction procedure : Capric acid (3.0 g) impregnated on silica gel was loaded in the chromatographic column and pH of the exchanger bed was adjusted to the desired value with the buffer solution. An aliquot containing 80.4 µg of Zr^{IV} was mixed with acetic acid (10 ml) and its pH was adjusted to 2.5. It was passed through the

pretreated column at a flow rate 1 ml min⁻¹. After extraction, Zr^{IV} was stripped with different mineral acids. A number of fractions were collected and the amount of Zr^{IV} from each fraction was determined spectrophotometrically¹⁰ using alizarin red S at 525 nm.

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References

1. H. GREEN, *Talanta*, 1973, **20**, 158.
2. N. NAKUSUKA, K. HIROSE and M. TANAKA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 265.
3. N. NAKASUKA, Y. NITSUOKA and M. TANAKA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 431.
4. P. NARAYANAN and S. M. KHOPKAR, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1985, **8**, 765.
5. CHEN, PEIXIAN, WANG and XIAOYING, *He Huaxue Yu Fangshe Hauxue*, 1991, **13**, 150.
6. D. K. GHOSH and U. S. ROY, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 344.
7. R. PRIBIL, "Chemometry, Basic Determination", Chemapol, Praha, 1961.
8. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of EDTA", New York, 1967.
9. S. N. BHOSALE and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Talanta*, 1976, **26**, 889.
10. E. B. SANDELL, "Colourimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959.